

Strengthening smoking cessation through routine screening, physician-delivered counseling, and treatment of tobacco-related co-morbidities in low and middle-income countries

Aanuoluwapo Adeyimika AFOLABI^{1*}, Olayinka Stephen ILESANMI²

Cite this paper as: Afolabi AA, Ilesanmi OS. Strengthening smoking cessation through routine screening, physician-delivered counseling, and treatment of tobacco-related co-morbidities in low and middle-income countries. *Adv Med Psychol Public Health*. 2025;2(3):207-209.

Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13630981

Received: 10 April 2024

Revised: 15 May 2024

Accepted: 30 July 2024

Published Online: 02 September 2024

¹Technical Services Directorate, MSI Nigeria Reproductive Choices, Abuja. Plus-Circle Community Health Advancement Organization, Nigeria. E-mail: afoannade@gmail.com ORCID: 0000-0001-9928-2252

²West Africa Regional Coordination Centre, Africa Centre for Disease Control, Abuja, Nigeria. Plus-Circle Community Health Advancement Organization, Nigeria. E-mail: ileolasteve@yaboo.co.uk ORCID: 0000-0003-0827-6442

Abstract

The global burden of tobacco use disproportionately affects low and middle-income countries (LMIC) where over 80% of the world's tobacco users reside. Despite the significant health risks, smoking cessation interventions are not prioritized in LMIC. This letter-to-the-editor advocates for strengthening smoking cessation efforts in LMIC by integrating routine screening for tobacco use, physician-delivered counseling, and the treatment of tobacco-related co-morbidities into standard healthcare practices. By normalizing the discussion around smoking cessation and providing tailored interventions, healthcare providers can more effectively support smokers in quitting, ultimately improving public health outcomes and reducing the burden of tobacco-related co-morbidities.

Take-home message: Implementing routine screening for tobacco use, coupled with physician-delivered counseling and treatment of tobacco-related co-morbidities, are crucial in enhancing smoking cessation efforts in low and middle-income countries, thereby reducing the substantial health burden associated with tobacco use.

Keywords: Low and middle-income countries; physician counseling; routine screening; smoking cessation; tobacco-related co-morbidities.

INTRODUCTION

More than 80% of the world's 1.3 billion tobacco users live in low- and middle-income countries (LMIC)[1]. Globally, tobacco use accounts for more than 8 million preventable deaths annually [1]. Approximately 7 million of these deaths are the consequence of direct tobacco use while the remaining result from indirect exposure to smoke, that is, second-hand smoke. Quitting smoking is arguably the most potent and economical approach in healthcare settings to prevent tobacco-related diseases, disabilities, and fatalities [2,3]. The persistent toll and substantial expenses caused by tobacco addiction underscore the critical importance of prioritizing tobacco control and smoking cessation as fundamental goals in public health. Strengthening smoking cessation through routine screening, physician-delivered counseling, and treatment of tobacco-related co-morbidities in LMIC are comprehensive approaches to help individuals quit smoking successfully.

By incorporating regular screening for tobacco use during routine healthcare visits, healthcare providers can identify smokers and offer timely interventions to help them quit [4,5]. Routine screening for smoking cessation has several benefits. Firstly, it increases awareness among smokers about the detrimental effects of tobacco on their health, encouraging them to take proactive steps towards quitting. Secondly, it enables healthcare providers to assess the severity of nicotine addiction, tailoring interventions accordingly, such as providing counseling, nicotine replacement therapy, or other evidence-based treatments. Moreover, incorporating smoking cessation into routine screenings normalizes the discussion around quitting smoking, reducing stigma, and fostering a more open dialogue between patients and healthcare professionals in LMIC. By leveraging their medical expertise, physicians can assess an individual's tobacco use history, identify personal motivations to quit, and tailor cessation strategies to suit their unique needs. Furthermore, physicians can offer evidence-based advice on nicotine replacement therapies and other pharmaceutical aids, enhancing the chances of successful quitting. Furthermore, routine screening contributes to mitigating secondhand smoke exposure and protecting non-smokers from harmful health effects of second-hand smoking.

The treatment of tobacco-related co-morbidities plays a pivotal role in enhancing smoking cessation among addicts in LMIC. When individuals with nicotine addiction are grappling with co-existing health conditions aggravated by tobacco use, addressing these co-morbidities becomes crucial for successful quitting outcomes. Treating tobacco-related co-morbidities such as respiratory diseases (e.g., chronic obstructive pulmonary disease) and cardiovascular disorders (e.g., hypertension) directly improves the overall health status of the addict. As their health improves, addicts become more motivated to quit smoking to prevent further damage to their already compromised health.

In conclusion, strengthening smoking cessation through routine screening is a powerful approach to tackling the pervasive issue of tobacco use in LMIC. It empowers healthcare providers to intervene early and provide targeted support, resulting in improved health outcomes for smokers and the wider community. By prioritizing and implementing such initiatives, we can make significant strides toward a smoke-free future and promote a healthier society for people living in LMIC.

Author Contributions: Conceptualization: AA; resources: AA; writing—original draft preparation: AA; writing—review and editing, AA and OI; supervision: OI; project administration: AA and OI. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This article received no external funding.

Acknowledgments: None.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Disclaimer/Publisher's Note: The Publisher remains neutral regarding jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations. Additionally, the Publisher is not responsible for the accuracy, completeness, or validity of the content of scientific articles published herein. This statement exempts the Publisher from any responsibility regarding the content of scientific articles, which is solely the responsibility of the authors and peer reviewers.

References

1. World Health Organization. Tobacco. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/tobacco>. Accessed 23 July 2023.
2. Golechha M. Health Promotion Methods for Smoking Prevention and Cessation: A Comprehensive Review of Effectiveness and the Way Forward. *Int J Prev Med.* 2016;7:7. doi: 10.4103/2008-7802.173797.
3. Reddy KS, Gupta PC. Tobacco control in India. New Delhi: Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India; 2004.
4. Spohr SA, Nandy R, Gandhiraj D, Vemulapalli A, Anne S, Walters ST. Efficacy of SMS text message interventions for smoking cessation: A meta-analysis. *J Subst Abuse Treat.* 2015;56:1–10.
5. Bala MM, Strzeszynski L, Topor-Madry R, Cahill K. Mass media interventions for smoking cessation in adults. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2013;6:CD004704. doi: 10.1002/14651858.CD004704.pub4.

Copyright: © 2025 by the authors. Submitted for possible open-access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).